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Influence of Parents' Level of Education and Occupation on the Academic Achievement of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students of Technical Colleges of Adamawa State

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to investigate the influence of parents' level of education and parents' occupation on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa State. The study has two specific purposes and two research questions. Similarly, two hypotheses were formulated and tested at alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The area of the study is Adamawa State of Nigeria. The population for the study comprised ninety four Senior Secondary School year three electrical installation and maintenance works trade students in the three State technical colleges in Adamawa State. There was no sampling as the entire population was studied. The instrument used for the study was standardized achievement test questions adopted from NABTEB past question papers. Validity of the instrument was ascertained through face and content validity. Test re-test method of establishing reliability was used and the reliability index was computed by correlating the two scores using Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. The data were analyzed using SPSS (version 22). Mean and Standard deviation was computed using SPSS to answer all the Research Questions. ANOVA was used to test the two hypotheses. Findings were made based on the research questions and hypotheses, among them are: Parents level of education and parents' occupation has no significant influence on the academic achievement of EIMW Students. It was therefore recommended that, Parents who are not educated or have low educational level should endeavour to allow the students take extra- coaching class to improve their academic performance.

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Introduction

Education is the best legacy parents can give to their children. The development of the nation starts from the family. When the family succeeds in teaching and impacting good values in their children, the country becomes a better place to live in. It is generally believed that the basis for any true development must commence with the development of human resources. Formal education is the demonstration of such desires to effectively and efficiently build a sound and strong economy. Education is a process by which the mind of human being develops through learning at homes, colleges or universities. It is also a process whereby a person develops attitudes and abilities that are considered to have value and relevance in the society. Every nation hoping to have bright future needs to emphasis education because it is the only way to much development. Yusuf and Al-Banawi (2013) noted that education must be considered as a key investment in modern economies because, as previously seen within the framework of a knowledge-based economy, there are strong and positive correlation between economic activity and education in explaining economic growth. Asiru (2014) stated that education is a catalyst to the development of individuals, society and the nation as a whole. Dagbo (2014) also opined that education in an important tool for social growth, development and interaction of all elements in the society for it economics, social and political well-being. Olayanju (2014) posited that education plays a critical role in human capacity building and skills acquisition.

Academic achievement is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment but there is no general agreement on how it is best tested or which aspects is most important-procedural knowledge such as skills or declarative knowledge such as facts (Wikipedia contributors, 2014). Individual differences in academic performance have been linked to differences in intelligence and personality. Students with higher mental ability as demonstrated by IQ tests and those who are higher in conscientiousness (linked to effort and achievement motivation) tend to achieve highly in academic settings. According to Kukwi and Amuche (2013) in educational institutions, success is measured by academic performance, or how well a student meets standards set out by the institution itself even though grades do not always reflect a person's knowledge or intelligence. According to Abdu-raheem (2015), the importance of academic achievement in one's life cannot be over-emphasized as it acts as an emotional tonic of sound academic records on which the entire future disposition stands. Abdu-raheem (2015), stress that academic achievement has always been the centre of educational research and despite varied definitions about the aims of education, the academic development of the child continues to be the primary and most important goal of education, life in general and for a student in particular has become highly competitive, today there is no place for a mediocre student. Anthony (2012) stressed the importance of scholastic academic achievement and the factors responsible for academic achievement, Anthony (2012) raised many important questions for educational researchers such as; what factors promote achievement in students? How far do the different factors contribute towards academic achievement? In this context, the role of parents academic attainment cannot be denied as it has a great effect on the learning and development of the child and his academic achievement.

Parental education is an important aspect of the students' academic achievement because it is expected that parental and student education is significantly correlated. Peters and Mullis (1997) concluded that parental education had a significant effect on academic achievement. Caldas and Bankston (1997) found that parental educational background and occupational status had significant effects on academic achievement than family income alone. A number of studies have recommended that parents that are educated engaged more in their children's education as compared to the parents that are less educated and that greater parental participation and involvement promotes more positive

attitudes toward school, improves homework habits, reduces absenteeism and dropping out, and enhances academic achievement (Muller, 1993; Stevenson and Baker, 1987;). An earlier study by James (2002) also showed that parental education levels exposed the clearest patterns of variation in student attitudes towards school and post school options. In the same way, Western (1998) found that students whose parents had high educational levels had access to a variety of resources which assisted and facilitated to participate in university studies. Ahmed (1991) arrived at the result that out of 56 candidates who had qualified the competitive examination for public sector jobs at the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Provincial Public Commission Pakistan, 30 of the candidates had parents with Bachelor and above educational qualifications. Krashen (2005) found that students whose parents are educated score higher on standardized tests as compared to those whose parents were not educated. According to Grissmer (2003) parents' level of education is the most important factor affecting students' academic achievement. Taiwo (1993) submits that parents' educational background influence the academic achievement of students. This, according to (Taiwo, 1993) is because the parents would be in a good position to be second teachers to the child; and even guide and counsel the child on the best way to perform well in education and provide the necessary materials needed by the child. This was supported by Musgrave (2000) who said that a child that comes from an educated home would like to follow the steps of his or her family and by this, work actively in his or her studies. Musgrave (2000) further said that parents who have more than a minimum level of education are expected to have a favored attitude to the child's education and to encourage and help him or her with school work, they provide library facilities to encourage the child to show examples in activities of intellectual type such as reading of newspapers, magazines and journals, they are likely to have wider vocabulary by which the children can benefit and develop language fluency. Onocha (1985) concludes that a child from a well educated family with high socio-economic status is more likely to perform better than a child from an illiterate family, this is because the child from an educated family has a lot of support such as a decent and good environment for academic work, parental support and guidance, enough textual and academic materials and decent feeding, more so, is likely to be sent to good schools where well seasoned teachers will handle his or her subjects.

According to William (2000) occupation is a person's regular work or profession, job or principal activity that serves as one's regular source of livelihood. He said occupation prestige as one component of socioeconomic status encompasses both income and education attainment, as it reflects the educational attainment required to obtain the job and income levels that vary with different jobs and within ranks of occupations. Additionally, it shows achievement in skills required for the job, occupational status measures social position by describing job characteristics, decision making ability and control and psychological demand on the job. Occupation is the most difficult factor to measure because so many exist and there are so many competing scales, many scales rank occupations based on the level of skill involve; from unskilled to skilled, manual labour to professional or use a combined measure using the education level needed and income involved. There are parents whose work do not give them time for their children as such the students are affected negatively (Duke, 2000; Sewell, William, Robert, and Hauser 1975;). They said most time you discover that most students or children are influenced by the occupation of their parents or stimulated by what they find their parents doing, parental or family set-standard may greatly affect performance of their children either positive or negatively even in the occupational choice of their children later in their lives and so motivate them to be achievement oriented. They further said families where some particular careers are of great priority tend to orient its children towards achieving that goal, in some families because the family head is a lawyer the children will want to be lawyer or even doctors, nurse or teachers or accountants because their parents are one or have set such standard for them. Studies by Halsey, Health and Ridge (1980) have shown that a child particular socio- economic inheritance may have a

direct and important effect on the career open or attractive to him than does his physical inheritance, the economic and occupational level of home affects the vocational goals of the youth by influencing their aspirations to be similar to those held by their parents and by discouraging aspirations to levels much above or below the parental occupational.

The foregoing discussion had established that parents' level of education and parents' occupation could have effects on children academic achievement. It is against this background that this work is being undertaken to empirically investigate the influence of these factors on Electrical Installation and Maintenance works trade students' academic achievement in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the fact that the development of any nation depends largely on the quality of education of her citizen, the academic performance of most Nigerian youth in technical colleges is decreasing. This has become a major concern of education stake-holders and researchers. Imogie (2002) drew attention to the public outcries concerning the low quality of education in Nigeria as there has been a persistent poor performance of Electrical Engineering trade students over the years in Technical Colleges of Adamawa State, particularly in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade (Adamawa State Educational Resource Centre NABTEB 2013). The Government of Nigeria is emphasizing on poverty eradication and job creation through Vocational and Technical Education and Training. Technical colleges are established to inculcate these basic technical skills which could make the graduates self reliant after graduation. If this current trend of poor performance of students in Technical colleges is not adequately addressed, it is apparently clear that the dream of achieving self reliance, job creation and poverty eradication may be an illusion after all. Several literatures such as; Ige (2007), Abdu-Raheem (2010) and Hassan (1983) confirmed different factors that could affect the students' academic achievement. Some of these factors are: inadequate funding, family size and family background of students among others.

Different studies have been carried out to prove the effect of socioeconomic status of parents on the academic achievement of students (Ugoji (2008), Eweniyi 2005) and Adeyemi in Abdu-Raheem (2010), however, study on the influence of parents level of education and parents occupation on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students' has not been ascertain in the recent past. It is against this background that this study is being undertaken to investigate the influence of parents' level of education and parents' occupation on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students of technical colleges in Adamawa state.

Purpose of the Study

The study is guided by two purposes as stated below:

1. To determine the influence of parents' level of education on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students of technical colleges in Adamawa state.
2. To determine the influence of parents' occupation on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students of technical college in Adamawa state.

Research Questions

Two research questions were formulated in accordance with the purpose of the study as follows:

1. What influence does parents' level of education have on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa State?
2. What influence does parents' occupation home environment have on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students based on their parents' level of education in electrical installation and maintenance work Achievement Test in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students based on their parents' occupation in electrical installation and maintenance work Achievement Test in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

Research design of the Study

The study adopted descriptive survey research design, survey research design was considered appropriate for this study because the study involves the collection of data from the respondents of the sample on the influence of parents' level of education and parents' occupation on EIMW students' academic achievement.

Area of the Study

The area of the study was Adamawa State of Nigeria. The population of the study comprise of 94 SS III students of electrical installation and maintenance work trade of the three state owned technical colleges in Adamawa State. This comprises 17 EIMW students from technical college Numan, 40 EIMW students from technical college Yola and 37 EIMW students from technical college Mubi. There was no sampling, as the entire population was studied.

Method of Sample Analysis

The instruments which was adopted from NABTEB 2013 – 2016 past question papers was titled; ‘‘Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Achievement Test Questions’’ (EIMWTATQ). Consisting two sections, section A solicits for information about the parents' level of education and occupation. Section B consist of 50 objectives questions to determine electrical Installation and maintenance work trade student academic performance in Basic Electricity. The test which was adopted from NABTEB 2013 - 2016 past question papers was faced and content validated, to examine the language and clarity of items, assess the appropriateness of the questionnaire for collecting the needed information, assess the extent to which the questionnaire items cover the subject and make suggestion(s) of item(s) deemed relevant but not included or omitted in the research so as to improve the quality of the instrument. To establish the reliability of the instrument Test re-test method of establishing reliability was used and the reliability index was computed by correlating the two scores using Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula. A reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained.

Copies of the validated instrument was administered to the respondents by the researcher in person. The data collected was analyzed using Excel. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22.0) was used in computing Mean and Standard deviation which was used to answer the two Research Questions. ANOVA was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The achievement test was scored over one hundred percent and the scores were graded. In order to draw statistical inferences on the hypotheses guiding the study, if the calculated t-value is less than the t-critical, the null hypothesis is accepted otherwise it is rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What influence does parents' level of education have on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa State?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Test Scores of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students in Electrical Installation Based on Their Parents' Level of Education

Category of Respondents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Masters and PhD	38	38.00	5.28
HND and First Degree	19	28.74	4.28
NCE and OND	22	25.64	4.81
FSLC and SSCE	15	21.87	6.21

Table 1 showed that students whose parents have Masters and PhD degrees scored higher with mean scores of 38.00, than students whose parents have HND and First Degree with mean scores of 28.74, NCE and OND with mean scores of 25.64 and FSLC and SSCE with mean scores of 21.87. Therefore it follows that differences exist in the mean achievement scores of EIMW students based on their parents' levels of education.

Research Question 2: What influence does parents' occupation have on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa State?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Test Scores of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students in Electrical Installation Based on Their Parents' Occupation

Category of Respondents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Civil Servants	57	34.18	7.31
Self Employed	29	23.52	5.72
Politicians	8	31.50	4.11

Table 2 showed that students whose parents are civil servant scored higher with mean achievement scores of 34.18, than students whose parents are self employed with mean scores of 23.52 and students whose parents are politicians with mean scores of 31.50. Therefore it follows that the parents' occupations determine the academic achievement of EIMW students.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students based on their parents' level of education in electrical installation and maintenance work Achievement Test in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

Table 3: Summary of ANOVA Results of the Difference in the Achievement Test Scores of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students Based on Their Parents' Level of Education

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	α	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Group	3832.60	3	1277.53	0.05	48.18	0.00	Reject H ₀₂
Within Group	2386.51	90	26.51				
Total	6219.11	93					

Table 3 showed the analysis of variance in the mean achievement test scores of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students based on their parents' level of education, F= 48.18, df= 3, $\alpha = 0.05$, P = 0.00. The F- calculated was 48.18, is greater than the Sig. value of 0.05. This signifies that significance difference exist in the achievement test scores of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students based on their parents' level of education. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant differences in the mean achievement scores of students based on their parents' level of education was rejected. This implies that parents' level of education have significant influence on the students' academic achievement. To determine exactly where the difference among the groups occur a post-hoc test of multiple comparison using Turkey Honest Significance Difference (HSD) was conducted in Table 4.

Table 4: Multiple Comparison of the Influence of Parents' Level of Education on the Academic Achievement of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students

(I) Education	(J) Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Master and PhD	HND and First Degree	9.26316*	1.44687	0.000
	NCE and OND	12.36364*	1.37953	0.000
	SSCE and FSLC	16.13333*	1.57022	0.000
HND and First Degree	Master and PhD	-9.26316*	1.44687	0.000
	NCE and OND	3.10048	1.61274	0.226
	SSCE and FSLC	6.87018*	1.77860	0.001
NCE and OND	Master and PhD	-12.36364*	1.37953	0.000
	HND and First Degree	-3.10048	1.61274	0.226
	SSCE and FSLC	3.76970	1.72427	0.135
SSCE and FSLC	Master and PhD	-16.13333*	1.57022	0.000
	HND and First Degree	-6.87018*	1.77860	0.001
	NCE and OND	-3.76970	1.72427	0.135

Table 4 showed multiple comparison of influence of parents' level of education on the academic achievement of EIMW students. The result of the analysis shows that significant difference exist in the mean achievement test scores of EIMW students based on their parents' level of education. The difference lies between HND and First Degree with NCE and OND (which was 0.226), then NCE and OND with FSLC and SSCE (which was 0.135) all at 0.05 level of significance. These differences however suggest that parents with high level of education are likely the ones who pay more attention on the education of their wards.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students based on their parents' occupational in electrical installation and maintenance work Achievement Test in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

Table 5: Summary of ANOVA Results of the Difference in the Achievement Test Scores of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students Based on Their Parents' Occupation

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	α	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Group	2189.62	2	1092.81	0.05	24.73	0.00	Reject H_{03}
Within Group	4029.49	91	44.28				
Total	6219.11	93					

Table 5 showed the analysis of variance in the mean achievement test scores of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students based on their parents' occupation. $F=24.73$, $df=2$, $\alpha=0.05$, $P=0.00$. The F- calculated value was 24.73, is greater than the Sig. value of 0.05. This signifies that significance difference exist in the achievement test scores of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students based on their parents' occupation. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant differences in the mean achievement test scores of students based on their parents' occupation was rejected. This implies that parents' occupation influence students' academic achievement. To determine exactly where the differences among the groups occur, a post-hoc test of multiple comparisons using Turkey Honest Significance Difference (HSD) was conducted in Table 6.

Table 6: Multiple Comparison of the Influence of Parents' Occupation on the Academic Achievement of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students

(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.
		(I-J)		
Self employed	Civil Servants	-10.65820*	1.51781	0.000
	Politicians	-7.98276*	2.65743	0.010
Civil Servants	Self employed	10.65820*	1.51781	0.000
	Politicians	2.67544	2.51234	0.538
Politicians	Self employed	7.98276*	2.65743	0.010
	Civil Servants	-2.67544	2.51234	0.538

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 6 showed multiple comparison of influence of parents' occupation (Civil Servant, Self employed and Politician) on electrical installation and maintenance work trade students' academic achievement scores. The results of the analysis show that the significant difference that exists in the mean achievement test scores of EIMW students based on their parents' Occupation lies between Civil Servants and Politicians (which was, 0.538) at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, this could mean that Civil servants pay more attention to their wards' education than Politicians, since the mean achievement scores of students whose parents are civil servants was higher (at 34.18) than that of students whose parents are politicians (at 31.50) respectively.

Findings of the Study

Based on the results of the research questions and the formulated null hypotheses which guided the study, the findings of the study are as follows:

1. Parents' levels of education determine the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students. Also the result of the hypothesis shows there is significance difference in the achievement test scores of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students based on their parents level of education.
2. Parents' occupations determine the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students. Likewise, the result of the hypothesis shows there is significance difference in the achievement test scores of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students based on their parents occupation.

Discussion

The result of the finding with regards to research question one, revealed that parents level of education determine the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students, this is in line with the findings of Krashen (2005), Eamon (2005) Dearing, Kreider, Simpkins and Weiss (2006) and Farooq, et al (2011) who found out that parents level of education has great influence on the academic achievement of students, as those students whose parents are educated score higher on standardized tests as compared to those whose parents were not educate. They affirmed that educated parents can better communicate with their children regarding school works and activities and are more concerned and more effective in helping their children in academic work, in doing so; they are also able to supervise and monitor their children's academic progress. According to them this can in no small measure contribute to the academic progress of their children, but parents with low educational attainment mostly do not care to supervise their children academic achievement due to lack of sufficient knowledge to face the challenge and this will discourage the children and may lead to poor performance and even later on drop out of school because they will not cope with the way they are always failing among their classmates in viewed of that they emphases on the importance of literacy development which stretches far beyond children's school achievements. They said well- developed literacy ability is an important condition for children's development in other intellectual and social areas and vice-versa. Similarly, the result of the finding in respect of hypothesis one indicated that parent's level of education have significant influence on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students of technical colleges of Adamawa State, the finding is in line with that of Taiwo (1993), Peters and Mullis (1997), Suleiman, Hassan, Ishtiaq, Mohammad, Ullah Khan, and Zaib-un-Nisa (2012), Ahmad and Najeemah (2013), who in their separate found out that parents educational level has significant influence on the academic performance of students; they said parents' with a higher level of education can provide greater opportunities for intellectual stimulation than parents with lower level of education.

The result of the finding with regards to research question two revealed that parents occupation determine the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students, the finding is in agreement with that of Duke, (2000), William (2000) and Roberts (2007) who found that parents' occupation has influence on the academic achievement of students; the types of occupation parents are into predict the aspiration of the students hence improved their performance in schools. They said most time you discover that most students or children are influenced by the occupation of their parents or stimulated by what they find their parents doing, parental or family set-standard greatly affect the performance of the students. They also found that students' particular socio-economic inheritances have direct and important effect on the occupation open or attractive to the students than their physical inheritance and that the economic and occupational status of the parents affects the students by influencing their academic performance. The result of the finding in respect of hypothesis two indicated that parents' occupation has significant influence on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students of technical colleges of Adamawa State, the findings is in agreement with the findings of Saifi and Mehmood (2011) who in their study found out that parents' occupation have significant influence on students academic achievement; they also discovered that most students are influenced by the occupation of their parents' or stimulated by what they find their parents doing, they also found that families where some particular careers are of great priority they oriented their children towards achieving that goal. In some families because the family head is a lawyer the children want to be lawyers or even doctors, nurse or teachers or accountants because their parents are one or have set such standard for them.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made:

1. Students from high educational level parents' performed better academically than those from low level of education parents', this showed that parents level of education have significant influence on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

Students whose parents are civil servant performed better academically than those whose parents are self employed and politicians, this showed that parents' occupation have significant influence on the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students in technical colleges of Adamawa state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents who are not educated or have low educational level should endeavor to allow the students take extra-coaching class.

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